

Why Does Customer Relationship Management Exist

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Abstract

Customer Relationship Management (CRM), which gained rapid traction in the business world during the mid-1990s, soon lost its appeal due to numerous instances of failure, where substantial investments in system implementation failed to deliver the anticipated outcomes. The main reason for these failures was that businesses overly concentrated on the technological tools available at the time and their eagerness to use them while overlooking the core principles of the CRM approach, especially the strategic and human components. CRM is not just a technology; what truly matters are the business processes and human resources that implement them. Technology can only support these two essential components. Today, driven by advancements in information technology, shifts in consumer behavior and expectations due to e-commerce, mobile applications, and social media necessitate the redefinition and restructuring of CRM. In the Information Age, CRM has become indispensable for crafting, implementing, and enhancing value in the relationships between businesses and their customers. This paper discusses the reasons for CRM's existence and its fundamental philosophy. In addition, it focuses on definitions related to CRM, its historical development, and the various ways in which it is important for businesses and their customers.

Keywords: Customer Relationship Management, CRM, Relationship Marketing, Digital Transformation, Consumer Behavior, Business Strategy, Customer Value.

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Introduction

When the concept of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is considered in its simplest form, its history goes back to the first ever definition of a “customer.” However, CRM aims to convey far more than what each of the three words that make up the concept, individually or collectively, bring to mind. Just as phrases like “the customer comes first” or “everything is for the customer” have become fundamental principles accepted by businesses, CRM has moved far beyond being a mere “trend” and has become a necessity for all organizations, whether they are profit-oriented or not.

Although the management of customer relationships is not a new concept, both “customers” and “relationships” are in a state of constant change and transformation in the Information Age. The rapid advancements in information technologies have greatly expanded the possibilities of customer relationship management and, in a sense, have removed the previous limitations. In particular, the Information Age has created a network economy and accelerated and facilitated communication among individuals and nodes in this network.

Previously, CRM was developed and implemented at the departmental level, covering only certain functions within a business. Today, this has long been surpassed, and CRM is now conducted and managed at the organizational level. In the Information Age, knowledge of customers, market conditions, and competition must be distributed and processed throughout the organization in a networked manner. Businesses have started seeking ways to use CRM as a tool to achieve this goal. In the past, customer information was gathered in the sales department, information about markets and competitors in the marketing department, and information about payments and economic conditions in the finance department. The use of this scattered information for common objectives that serve the core goal of the business was a phenomenon that many companies found difficult or even unimaginable to achieve in the past. Therefore, CRM implementations attempted in the past have often failed for many businesses. The modern CRM approach, on the other hand, aims to transform this scattered and siloed data across different departments into information that can be used organization-wide, creating leverage and delivering benefits.

This study explores customer relationship management, its development, and its existence. Various definitions of CRM are presented, and the historical development of CRM theory is emphasized.

1. What is Customer Relationship Management?

As mentioned earlier, although it is possible to trace the origins of CRM all the way back to the first customer, this perspective is insufficient to explain modern commerce. Consumers, who in the recent past were limited to television, landline phones, or local

automobile manufacturers, have long since forgotten those challenging times. Moreover, the new generation perceives this recent past as distant as the Middle Ages that they read about in their middle-school textbooks. “The customer comes first” was hung on the wall as a slogan, but neither the “customer” nor “customer relations” were valued in practice.

If we look beyond history to the post-Industrial Revolution era, we see that developments in production made it possible to manufacture products more cheaply and quickly than before. Moreover, with advancing technology, new products can be offered to large populations. In the early 20th century, businesses primarily focused on production of their products. Before the marketing concept, this period included production, product, and sales approaches that lasted until after World War II. During this time, businesses viewed the “customer” merely as “the consumer who fulfills the payment.” After all, if one customer did not buy, there were plenty of others who would. Businesses were so focused on making and improving their products that they often ignored what their customers wanted.

Today, from Baudrillard’s (2004) “Consumer Society” to Schwatz’s (2008) “Paradox of Choice,” and from AltaVista to Google Mobile Services, and from multifunctional calculators to cloud computing, almost everything regarding customers and customer relations has changed. The contemporary CRM approach focuses on how businesses establish and manage relationships with their customers—who now, more than ever, can easily access information, products, and competitors. When considered as a system, CRM encompasses the efficient management of all interactions a business conducts with its customers, including how businesses work with their customers, how they solve their problems, how they manage every stage of the customer journey from the purchase decision to disposal, and how they convince customers to repeatedly buy their products and services. With this management, the goal is not only to achieve benefits such as profit, turnover, and market share for the business but also to create tangible value for customers—values that are recognized and appreciated by them.

CRM proactively and intelligently addresses all interactions with customers, both inside and outside the business, as well as all business functions related to these interactions. To implement this approach, it is essential to utilize all existing and emerging technologies to align business processes with customer relationship management processes. Achieving this is complex and challenging. Because most business processes are already centered around dealing with customers, successfully implementing a healthy CRM approach requires the reconfiguration of all functions and the design of systems in this direction.

Since CRM encompasses all the rules regarding every point of contact with the customer and the supporting functions, it can no longer be left solely to the sales or marketing departments, as in the past. Indeed, the responsibilities allocated to sales and marketing are exclusively related to operations. However, CRM plays a crucial role in decision-making from both strategic and analytical perspectives. The collection, evaluation, and conversion

of data into information, and making that information available at the right place, at the right time, to the right people within the organization, are fundamental for CRM success and are the key distinguishing features of this approach.

Therefore, with the support of top management, all departments in the business—regardless of how different their activities may seem—must be brought together on a single plane centered around the “customer.” Conversely, when CRM is perceived solely as software, as was historically the case, its primary objective is undermined. For example, if a sales representative only logs customer visits into the system because their supervisor demands it but does not record complaints; if the returns department quickly finalizes returns received from customers without informing marketing; if the call center gives potential customers contact information when they inquire about purchasing a product but does not notify sales for follow-up; or if the finance department, without any evaluation, instantly halts the shipment of a strategic customer just because their payment is one day late, then CRM cannot be said to be properly understood and implemented in that business.

1.1. CRM Definitions

CRM is a strategic management approach designed to minimize operational costs across organizations while enhancing customer loyalty. CRM facilitates the development of a comprehensive understanding of the customer by integrating data collected from various customer interaction points, both internal and external to the organization, and from all other customer-related processes. When this is achieved, the information needed by departments such as sales, customer support, and marketing can be instantly accessed and shared.

In general, CRM is an approach used by businesses to get to know their customers, understand their needs and behaviors, and establish long-term relationships with them. This approach is based on the principle that the key to success for any business lies with the customer. Therefore, although CRM has many technological components, it cannot be reduced to these tools alone. This customer-centric approach to business has three fundamental dimensions:

- Processes
- Technology
- Employees

The most important component of CRM is the process. This process involves collecting and using customer information to create value for both businesses and customers. The realization of this value is contingent upon employees. Technology, on the other hand, refers to all the tools employees use in these processes to create value. For CRM success, it is essential to train and guide employees properly, design processes correctly, and select appropriate technologies. However, this requires effective change management. Rooted in

the philosophy of “people first,” the most essential requirements are understanding, training, and persuading individuals to align with business goals. Subsequently, all business processes should be restructured to deliver value to the customers. It is essential to thoroughly understand existing processes, focusing on identifying which processes generate customer value and which can be improved. During the process improvement phase, determining the amount of investment made for each process is also critically important for CRM success. In these improvement and design steps, customer information obtained from the business’s data sources will serve as a guide. From the top manager to the lowest level employee, everyone in the business must adopt the CRM approach to ensure the success of the efforts made. Therefore, it is one of the main elements that businesses must focus on to ensure business continuity.

From the mid-1990s onwards, CRM, which was initially promoted as a product to be sold to businesses primarily by the information technology industry, began to find a place in academic literature as well (Srivastava, Shervani, and Fahey, 1999). Some definitions related to CRM are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Definitions of CRM

Author	Definition
Glazer (1997)	CRM seeks to build a strategic bridge between information technologies and marketing strategies for the purpose of establishing long-term relationships and improving profitability.
Peppers, Rogers, and Dorf (1999)	CRM is the application of one-to-one and relationship marketing based on what is known about individual customers and what they communicate.
Couldwell (1999)	CRM encompasses the use of current customer information to enhance business profitability and customer service.
Gosney and Boehm (2000)	Although CRM has many different dimensions, the fundamental aspect for the business is being more customer-centric.
Swift (2000)	CRM is a business approach requiring meaningful communication that aims to acquire new customers, retain existing ones, and improve customer loyalty and profitability by understanding and influencing customer behavior
Buttle (2001)	CRM is about developing mutually beneficial relationships with strategically important customers over the long term.
Paravativar and Sheth (2001)	CRM encompasses the processes and comprehensive strategies used to acquire, retain, and develop relationships with selected customers.
Stone and Woodcock (2001)	CRM refers to the methods, technology, and e-commerce capabilities used by a business to manage relationships with its customers.

Source: Adapted from Wübben (2008).

The definitions in Table 1 share common points as well as certain shortcomings. Payne and Frow (2005), who define CRM as “a strategic approach aimed at increasing a company’s shareholder value by establishing appropriate relationships with key customers and customer segments,” outline the main aspects of CRM as follows:

- CRM aims to develop profitable and long-term relationships with customers and stakeholders by combining the strengths of relationship marketing and information technology.
- CRM seeks to understand customer needs on a data-driven basis and create value with customers as equal contributors.
- Through its technology-based applications, CRM enables different departments within the company to jointly manage processes, human resources, operations, and marketing competencies as cross-functional teams to achieve the stated objectives.

1.2. The Three Fundamental Dimensions of CRM

Various definitions of CRM emphasize the strategic management of customer relationships (Meadows and Dibb, 2012), enhancement of customer process competencies through technological tools (Maklan, Knox and Peppard, 2011), and design of all customer-oriented company activities centered around information management (Padilla-Melendez and Garrido-Moreno, 2013). Defining CRM as a technology would mean ignoring the true purpose of this approach. Based on Payne and Frow’s (2005) definition, the development of attributions related to CRM is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: CRM Journey

Source: Payne and Frow (2005)

Based on the definitions of different researchers, it can be said that CRM has three main components as shown in Figure 2: (1) operational, (2) analytical, and (3) collaborative.

Figure 2: The Structure of CRM

Source: Alavi, Ahuja and Medury (2012)

1.2.1. Operational

The operational dimension of CRM encompasses a business’s outward-facing processes, such as sales, customer support and customer service (Mosadegh and Behboudi, 2011). Many processes carried out at these touchpoints, where direct contact with customers occurs, are highly operational. CRM technologies enable the automation of processes related to call centers, field services, and sales force management (Sen and Sinha, 2011). In this way, the necessary information for preparing and delivering customer proposals, finding new customers, and responding to customer requests is instantly made available to relevant personnel (Alavi et al., 2012). This dimension of CRM also includes elements such as order management, invoicing, and other aspects of customer service.

The operational dimension of CRM also involves collecting data voluntarily provided by customers through tools such as websites, mobile applications and kiosks. This makes it possible to track and proactively respond to requests from customers who search the website, show interest in a campaign, and register even before those requests turn into sales.

1.2.2. Analytical

The management of the massive amount of data collected during the operational stages is one of the most fundamental issues in CRM performance. Converting data into information that holds value for both customers and businesses falls within the analytical dimension of CRM (Alavi et al., 2012). As a result, general and/or subjective trends in customer behavior

can be defined using the collected data, and it becomes possible to prepare new recommendations by leveraging previous habits of customers. This process can also be described as uncovering customers' hidden knowledge. The analytical dimension of CRM includes the steps of "collecting, storing, filtering, integrating, managing, and sharing" customer data (Gulliver, Joshi, and Michell, 2013). The aim is to make the right information available in the right place and at the right time, tailored to the customer's situation and their characteristics. The analytical dimension covers data warehousing, simulation, forecasting, data mining, and online analytical processing (OLAP: Online Analytical Processing protocols) (Shanks and Bekmamedova, 2012).

Thanks to the tools incorporated in this software dimension of CRM, customer behavior patterns can be discovered, and each behavior can be analyzed accordingly; thus, cross-selling, upselling, increasing the share of wallet, and detecting fraudulent transactions involving different parties become possible (Ranjan and Bhatnagar, 2011). Analytical systems operate automatically to prepare offers for selling different products to new customers, monitor the activity status of existing customers, analyze lost customers, and present the results to relevant units in real time.

1.2.3. Collaboration

CRM enhances communication among all stakeholders involved in delivering value to customers and plays a role in the business's processes with its customers. CRM offers increased collaboration in both internal and external processes, harmonizes relationships, and manages and organizes communication (Rodriguez and Honeycutt, 2011). The collaboration dimension of CRM further strengthens the relationships among the stakeholders throughout the entire supply chain. The main purpose of this dimension is to systematically deliver the insights obtained from the analytical dimension to the operational dimension for its execution.

The subcomponents of the collaboration dimension are all communication tools within a business (Alavi et al., 2012). All communication tools must be integrated and coordinated for CRM performance. Thus, even if customers are contacted at different times via different channels, a single, unified customer experience can still be created. CRM's collaboration dimension also allows employees outside the sales and marketing departments to access the necessary level of customer and market information to improve their performance. Today, as a requirement of the business models in various industries, suppliers or selected business partners can access the necessary information to the extent to which they are permitted to. Similarly, information collected from business partners is retained within the organization. In this way, multi-component and holistic data can be delivered to the analytical dimension of customer management.

2. The Development of Customer Relationship Management

The “marketing mix” proposed by Jerome McCarthy in the 1960s provided a framework for businesses to increase market demand and sales. In this context, companies seek ways to increase demand for their products through decisions regarding product, price, place, and promotion. The marketing mix, a transactional approach, was concerned with which component businesses should invest in and to what extent, to maximize profitability. During this period, alongside the traditional “promote the product and wait, adjust price to maximize profit” approach, which businesses had previously adopted, direct marketing efforts began to emerge with the development of customer-centric marketing (Dyche, 2002). This method, which required more communication with customers, generally operated within the boundaries of the mass communication tools of the time, aiming for the customer to choose the most suitable option among limited choices. The scarcity of options may have partially reduced customer expectations regarding the offered product/service.

In the 1980s, Arndt (1979), Bagozzi (1978), Dwyer, Schurr, and Oh (1987), and Levitt (1983) argued that businesses should focus on long-term relationships rather than short-term transactions and stressed that relationships among various stakeholders should be addressed in an integrative way. At that time, marketing was considered a single department within a business. Contrary to this view, the relationship marketing approach redefines the market and aims to manage the relationships among all stakeholders of the business—customers, employees, shareholders, etc., who may sometimes have conflicting objectives—in a way that produces positive outcomes for all parties involved (Berry, 1983). Therefore, it is beneficial to briefly discuss relationship marketing theory.

2.1. Relational Marketing Theory

In the transition from a transactional approach, where costs and functionality are prioritized, to a relational approach, as shown in Figure 3, marketing activities managed by a single department give way to cross-functional teams involving other departments. Similarly, relationship marketing emphasizes acquiring new customers and retaining existing ones. To retain customers, it is important to understand and communicate with them; however, this is insufficient. For this purpose, it is also necessary to understand the different stakeholders who communicate with the customers. Later, topics such as customer lifetime value emerged.

Figure 3: Transition to Relationship Marketing

Source: Payne (2005)

In relationship marketing, significant emphasis is placed on transforming particularly profitable customers into loyal patrons of the business, with a focus on the customer lifetime value (Berry, 1983). The concept of customer lifetime value, defined as the present value of the total net profit estimated to be generated by customers for the business in future periods, highlights that not every customer holds the same level of importance for the business and that marketing strategies should be developed for profitable customers with whom it is possible to build long-term relationships by creating value for them, in line with the goals of the business (Dwyer, 1989).

Contrary to the transactional approach, relationship marketing aims to establish sustainable and profitable relationships (Sen and Sinha, 2011). Therefore, product-based marketing activities have been replaced by consumer-based marketing activities. Loyalty programs, company-branded credit cards, personalized offers, email lists, etc. (Ashley et al., 2011) are among the marketing practices that have emerged from relationship marketing approaches. The implementation and sustainable management of these activities have created a need for CRM tools to support these efforts.

2.2. CRM as a Technological Tool

With the proliferation of call centers and the emerging need to manage customer transactions in these centers, the first software products were introduced in the 1990s (Osarenkhoe and Bennani, 2007). The aim of these initial CRM examples was to automate customer processes found in certain business units and their functions. Software such as Siebel and Vantive (now known as PeopleSoft) sought to standardize areas such as sales force management and customer support, attracting significant interest in the market. These automation solutions mostly operated on local networks, and because they typically lacked business-specific customization, companies had to adapt their operational tasks to the software's workflows.

- The basic features offered in the first CRM systems were as follows:
- Creating scenarios and ready responses for telephone sales and phone support.
- Providing a workflow for the different steps of the sales process.

- Offering workflows that ensure coordination between different units regarding customer complaints and requests.
- Authorizing relevant departments of the business to access customer information.
- Contributing to the management of the sales teams.

In these systems, the success of the solutions created and the benefits obtained from CRM varied greatly from one business to another. In particular, while businesses with large sales teams, high sales volumes, and intense customer support could benefit from the system, businesses with business processes that software developers generally did not envisage remained distant from success because of the integration barriers they encountered. Most CRM investments made during this period were wasted because of insufficient consideration of the process and human dimensions (Frow et al., 2011). However, this situation could not go beyond providing colorful and more organized reports

2.3. The Proliferation of the Internet

With the widespread adoption of the Internet, especially the use of the web for commercial purposes, CRM has once again come to the forefront (Greenberg, 2010). Previously seen merely as a tool for automation and business development, advancements in Internet technologies have created endless possibilities for CRM to reach customers directly, collect customer data directly, sell directly to the customer, and solve customer problems.

Owing to the following features, the Internet has led to the rewriting of CRM rules and, so to speak, changed the game.

- 24/7 access
- Instant access to information about product features, pricing, and stock status
- The possibility in web browsing for shopping to access different products and businesses that provide these products from anywhere in the world
- Online customer support
- Creation and delivery of personalized content
- Instant messaging and live chat applications

With the features and opportunities mentioned above, CRM has become indispensable for businesses to respond successfully. The speed expectations of customers who have become acquainted with the Internet have changed entirely regarding the services they receive. Additionally, the implementation of activities that can be considered self-service from pre-sales to after-sales allows many business processes to be delegated to technological tools, enabling employee resources to be directed toward core objectives and used efficiently.

CRM is a business approach that brings together people, processes, and technology and aims to maximize relationships with customers. Thanks to the Internet and mobile technology, CRM can now be used in real time. Just as the human heart continues to beat

and pump blood even when asleep, organizations have become entities that monitor parameters such as customer demand, competitive analysis, inventory, supply opportunities, and profitability around the clock. With this new era in CRM development, businesses have gained the opportunity to interact live with their customers in the virtual environment about their products and themselves, share the information customers need and communicate effectively. Technological advances in the Internet have also led businesses to integrate CRM systems into their supply chains, allowing them to provide better service. However, as mentioned above, this does not occur in business structures that have not internalized the CRM mindset.

2.4. The Evolution of Customers

Thanks to the Internet, customers now have easy access to a wide range of information. Previously, there was an information asymmetry in favor of businesses regarding product benefits, costs, and alternatives. Today, with the proliferation of communication tools, a balance has been established in favor of the customers. In the Information Age, customers can access user experiences, product alternatives, and all their features from all over the world and, through B2B marketplaces, even gain insight into the true costs of products and services (Saarijarvi, Karjaluoto, & Kuusela, 2013). Therefore, control over shopping today often rests with customers. In market conditions where customers' knowledge and thus their expectations from businesses have increased, relationships with customers have become a value that is harder for competitors to copy than product or service features. In this context, businesses should ensure that every decision related to their marketing mix is in harmony with the holistic CRM strategies that have been previously established. CRM should not be considered simply as a tool but as a genetic code that permeates every fiber of the organization.

Digital technologies have changed customers' expectations and behaviors, their fundamental needs and desire to fulfill these needs have essentially remained unchanged. For example, watching television for entertainment has been replaced by YouTube, and listening to music through cassettes or CDs has been replaced by apps such as Spotify and Apple Music. These examples demonstrate that businesses must be customer-oriented rather than product-oriented and plan their futures accordingly to ensure their survival. Acquiring customers and, more importantly, retaining those relationships is costly for businesses. However, if this necessary investment in relationships is avoided, businesses will face customer attrition and, worse, may never understand why they are losing their customers. As acquiring new customers is more expensive than retaining existing customers, businesses should consider this when considering the financial aspects of their decisions.

Many CRM investments fail not because of the approach itself but because of inadequacies in planning, coordination, and implementation. When designing CRM processes, more

emphasis should be placed on the overall customer experience rather than simply producing good products or communicating correctly. In many cases, even if a customer is satisfied with the features, price, or information provided about a product, unresolved issues during their experience with the business can lead them to change their subsequent purchasing decisions, causing them to abandon the business altogether. Therefore, CRM technologies should be used to design and deliver customer experiences.

Conclusion

The primary goal of marketing and management strategies is to develop competitive advantages (Devlin and Ennew, 1997). Competitive advantage means promising customers superior value compared to rival businesses. According to Porter (1985), to achieve competitive advantage, businesses must either adopt a cost leadership strategy or differentiate their customer offerings from competitors in a unique and valuable manner. In today's market conditions—where new inventions can be quickly imitated by competitors, costs converge due to global players achieving economies of scale, and the market gravitates toward network economies—relationships established with customers present significant opportunities for differentiation. Therefore, successfully managing these relationships in a way that not only reduces costs but also differentiates from rivals and enables the acquisition of more customers is no longer a choice, but a fundamental necessity.

Various companies are attempting to optimize these structures. For example, Siemens has been implementing its CRM system for many years, not only at the lower and middle management levels but also in a way that encompasses relationships with customers established by employees at all levels, including higher-level directors and even members of the executive board (Senn, 2006). The company's main goal in this respect is to establish the highest level of commercial relationship with existing customers, especially those of strategic importance. The fact that a global company places such importance on CRM is not just for collecting customer data. Beyond this, it is about analyzing customer data, transforming it into information, using the information created to generate value for all stakeholders, and, thanks to the learnings obtained throughout the CRM journey, demonstrating organizational learning and development. Businesses that can achieve these goals can sustain their existence in markets characterized by intense competition and rapid change.

CRM requires ownership at the highest level, and one of the key factors in achieving success is the strategy set by top management (Nguyen and Mutum, 2012). One of the main challenges in customer relationship management is defining which department within the organization will take on what level of responsibility in implementing this approach and, overall, determining who will own the system. Many CRM initiatives established before the 2000s became victims of conflicts between different departments because of the

aforementioned misallocation of roles and responsibilities or because they were implemented without strategic direction from top management, and thus, failed to deliver the positive outcomes initially expected.

To truly benefit from CRM, various internal departments of a company must work together and coordinate their activities while establishing strong cooperation with relevant external stakeholders (Agrawal, 2004). Companies that successfully implement CRM experience positive results, such as increased customer satisfaction and loyalty, and also see improvements in sales and profitability. However, those who cannot establish CRM strategies or ensure cooperation and coordination fail to fully realize a return on their investments. In the Information Age, it is essential to act with the awareness that CRM offers far more opportunities across many sectors than ever before.

Author's Note

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